

FAIR principles in data life-cycles for Humanities

Introduction

This task aims to identify and develop use cases based on Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) communities engagement. In order to do that, we will rely on [consortia funded by Huma-Num](#) and other partners from DARIAH (e.g. Italy and Germany). Another focus will be done on the link between data and publication. HAL, the French national open archive created by CCSD, provide a specific portal for SSH communities to deposit and deliver [publications in open access](#).

CCSD will work with Huma-Num to link publications on HAL to research data in data repositories, especially [Nakala](#), the data repository from Huma-Num dedicated to SSH. This case will be **a model for linking with other data repositories used in SSH communities**.

The first step of **building the relationship between the publications deposited in HAL and the data deposited in Nakala** has been taken, using the APIs available in each of the repositories. The relations thus created will be displayed, exported and harvestable. In order to be able to synchronise the relationships established in both platforms, we did the technical choice of using the MERCURE protocol and installed a MERCURE server for this purpose.

Then the next steps are to be able to ensure that the links made manually between data and publications **can be synchronised** and shared at will.

USE CASE

EMAIL

adeline.joffres@huma-num.fr
benedicte.kuntziger@ccsd.cnrs.fr

COMMUNITIES

Humanities
Social sciences

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PARTNERS

CENTRE POUR
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SCIENTIFIQUE DIRECTE

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Challenges addressed

SSH are very fragmented and diverse. Presenting use cases representatives is a big challenge per se. So, gathering representatives use cases from CO-OPERAS community (SSH, scientific communication) and SSH in France is part of this work (Cf. MS24).

Our main focus represents in itself a challenge and a need widely shared in SSH communities: linking scientific publications with (raw) data stored in a structured and "FAIR" way in a secure repository. We thus decided to work on a POC consisting in linking publications in HAL (French Open archive) to data stored in the Nakala French repository dedicated to SSH (MS26). The implementation of this POC will address various core question to current research in SSH, as you can see in the video embedded on top of this page.

Finally, another big challenge is to imagine next uses and evolutions of the POC which could be replicated in other domains.

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Benefits through EOSC-Pillar

We can identify two main topics that SSH communities will benefit from the EOSC-Pillar project:

- ★ Engaging a **deep collaboration between two national infrastructures for SSH** that will surely have a following and will allow a better comprehension and integration of common interests and needs
- ★ Contributing to **promote and make accessible Open Science and FAIR data** processes and services
- ★ **Implementing new services** to be deepened later for French SSH communities

Highlights

Next challenge in parallel of the central Use Case 5 is to study in more details the links and possible collaborations between the use case on Lidar data and WP7 and turn it into another POC before the end of the project.

If the main highlight remains the **implementation of the POC between the HAL and NAKALA repositories** (in particular the synchronisation and exposition of relationships within both repositories), various extensions are envisaged. One of them will consist, if possible, in **allowing the simultaneous deposit of publications and data** in the same repository, HAL, and then transferring the data into Nakala, creating the relationship between the two repositories automatically, on the model of what has already been developed in HAL for software codes, in partnership with the Software Heritage repository. It is also conceivable, by means of a survey of users of the two data repositories, to deepen the bi-directional character of the “simple” link initially created, as well as its visualisation.

References

Joffres, Adeline, Larrousse, Nicolas, Barborini, Yannick, & Kuntziger, Bénédicte. (2020). EOSC-Pillar MS26: Communications Proof of Concept between NAKALA and HAL.

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